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Assessing the Integration of Digital Tools and Barriers on Access to Quality Education among Internally Displaced Children in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study evaluates the role of digital tools and barriers in accessing quality education among internally displaced children (IDCs) in Benue State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was employed, with a population of 68,076 school-age IDCs across six Local Government Areas. A sample of 384 participants was selected using multistage sampling. Data were collected using a validated structured questionnaire, Integration of Digital Tools and Barriers on Access to Quality Education among Internally Displaced Children Questionnaire (IDTBAQEIDCQ), which achieved a reliability coefficient of 0.89. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used for analysis. Findings indicate that digital tools; such as mobile learning apps, online video platforms, e-books, and educational websites significantly enhance access to and quality of education for IDCs. However, barriers like unreliable internet access, high device costs, limited electricity, low teacher digital literacy, and poor learning environments hinder effective technology adoption. The study highlights the need to integrate technology to address educational gaps for displaced learners. Key recommendations include scaling up successful digital platforms, improving infrastructure, and enhancing teacher training in digital literacy. These measures are critical to ensuring equitable and effective education for IDCs in Benue State.

Keywords: Assessment, Quality Education, Barriers, Internally Displaced Persons & Technology Tools

Introduction

Access to quality education is a significant challenge for internally displaced children (IDCs), especially in regions experiencing conflict, natural disasters, and other forms

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of instability. In Nigeria, the situation is particularly dire due to ongoing insurgencies, communal clashes, and farmer-herder conflicts, which have displaced millions, including a large number of children (Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre [IDMC], 2022). Benue State, located in North-Central Nigeria, has been heavily impacted by these crises, resulting in a sharp increase in internally displaced persons (IDPs), with children forming a significant portion of this population (National Emergency Management Agency [NEMA], 2021). Although the government and various non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have made efforts to provide educational opportunities for these children, substantial barriers remain, particularly at the post-primary education level.

Additionally, post-primary education is a critical stage in the development of children, as it equips them with essential skills for economic productivity and social integration (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2020). However, IDCs in Benue State face numerous obstacles, including insufficient infrastructure, a shortage of qualified teachers, and limited access to learning materials (Okeke & Eze, 2021). These challenges are further compounded by the psychological trauma associated with displacement, which often negatively impacts their ability to learn effectively (Save the Children, 2021).

In recent years, technological tools have emerged as potential solutions to improve access to quality education, especially in resource-limited settings. Digital platforms, mobile learning applications, and online resources have demonstrated the ability to enhance educational access, improve learning outcomes, and offer personalized learning experiences (West & Chew, 2014). However, the use of technology in education for IDCs is not without its challenges. Barriers such as limited access to electricity, low digital literacy among teachers and students, and the high cost of technological devices have been identified as significant obstacles (United Nations Children's Fund [UNICEF], 2020). Additionally, the unique needs of IDCs, including their psychosocial well-being and the transient nature of their living conditions, require a tailored approach to integrating technology into their education (Agu & Okeke, 2023).

Ultimately, this study provides a crucial examination of technological tools and barriers in facilitating access to quality education for internally displaced children (IDCs) in post-primary education in Benue State. By comparing this finding with existing literature, several key insights and gaps become evident. Omale, Abduljabbar, and Dauda (2022) address the urgent need to bridge educational gaps for IDCs through

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targeted interventions during emergencies. Their work emphasizes the necessity of tailored strategies to support displaced students but does not delve deeply into the specific technological tools and barriers that could address these gaps. Ambe-Uva (2012) also discusses the potential of open and distance learning as a means to uphold the right to education for displaced populations in Nigeria. This perspective is valuable but primarily focuses on higher-level educational solutions rather than the practical, on-the-ground impact of technological tools and barriers in post-primary education settings for IDCs.

The gap identified by this study is the need for a focused examination of how technological tools and barriers specifically impact the educational experiences and outcomes of IDCs in post-primary education in Benue State. While existing studies provide a general understanding of technology's role and the challenges faced by displaced populations, they do not offer a detailed assessment of how technological interventions can be tailored to the unique needs of IDCs in this specific educational context. This research aims to bridge this gap by providing a nuanced analysis of technological tools and barriers and offering actionable insights to develop more effective strategies for leveraging technology to enhance access to quality education for IDCs in Benue State.

While there is a growing body of research on the use of technology in education, there is limited focus on role of technological tools and barriers in improving access to quality education for IDCs, particularly at the post-primary level in conflict-affected regions like Benue State. Existing studies have primarily concentrated on primary education or general IDP populations, leaving a gap in understanding the specific challenges and opportunities at the post-primary level (Obiakor & Maltby, 2020). This study aims to address this gap by evaluating the role of technological tools in meeting the educational needs of IDCs in Benue State, while also identifying the barriers that hinder their effective implementation.

In conclusion, assessing the role of technological tools and barriers in facilitating access to quality education for internally displaced children in post-primary education in Benue State is both timely and critical. As the global community continues to address the challenges of displacement and educational inequality, this study offers a unique opportunity to explore innovative solutions that can transform the educational landscape for IDCs, contributing to their holistic development and future prospects.

Statement of the Problem

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This study addresses the pressing issue of internal displacement, with a specific focus on the vulnerable demographic of internally displaced children (IDCs) in Nigeria, particularly in Benue State. The unique challenges faced by IDCs include limited access to educational resources and difficulties in maintaining a consistent learning environment due to forced relocations and the resultant instability. The majority of these displaced children are denied a secure, inclusive, and quality education, exacerbating the short- and long-term consequences of their displacement (Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre [IDMC], 2020). Existing barriers, such as a lack of teaching capacity, limited funding, ongoing insecurity, social tensions, and discrimination, further compound the challenges faced by education systems in low-income and fragile contexts (IDMC, 2020).

Recognizing the potential of technology to address these issues, the study acknowledges the growing interest in adopting technology in Nigeria's education sector. Technological interventions, such as online learning platforms, mobile applications, and digital educational resources, have shown promise in enhancing educational access for marginalized populations, including IDCs. The study aligns with the perspective presented by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR, 2023), which views technology as a valuable tool for driving inclusion in education among displaced populations, transcending geographical constraints and bridging gaps created by displacement.

Despite numerous studies on internally displaced persons (IDPs), none have explored the influence of technological tools and barriers in facilitating access to quality education for internally displaced children in post-primary education in Benue State. Additionally, there is a lack of standardized structures, well-articulated plans, and procedures in Nigeria to address digital educational needs in emergencies. Given the contemporary and ongoing nature of this issue, a research gap has emerged, prompting this study to fill the void.

This study, therefore, seeks to assess the role of technological tools and barriers in facilitating access to quality education for internally displaced children in post-primary education in Benue State. By doing so, it aims to provide actionable insights into how technology can be effectively leveraged to address the unique educational challenges faced by IDCs, while also identifying the barriers that hinder its successful implementation. The findings of this study will contribute to the development of

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targeted strategies to improve educational outcomes for this vulnerable group, ultimately promoting inclusivity and equity in education.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this research is to examine the role of digital tools and barriers in accessing quality education among internally displaced children (IDCs) in Benue State, Nigeria. The specific objectives guiding the study are to:

- a) Ascertain the specific technological tools and platforms that has been most effective in facilitating access to and improving the quality of education for IDPs in Benue State?
- b) Find out the main challenges and barriers hindering the effective use of technology to facilitate access to quality education for IDPs in Benue State?

Research Questions

The following research questions were set out to guide the study:

- 1) What are the specific technological tools and platforms that have most effectively facilitated access to and enhanced the quality of education for IDPs in Benue State?
- 2) What are the main challenges and barriers hindering the effective use of technology to facilitate access to quality education for IDPs in Benue State?

Methodology

The research design for this study adopted a descriptive survey design to systematically collect and analyze data on the experiences of internally displaced children (IDCs) in post-primary schools across Benue State.

This design was appropriate for assessing the impact of technology on access to quality education without manipulating variables (Nworgu, 2015). The study was conducted in Benue State, focusing on three major IDP camps: Abagena (Makurdi), Gbajimba (Guma), and Anyiin (Logo).

These areas were selected due to their high concentration of displaced persons and evident challenges in accessing quality education. The population consisted of 68,076 school-age IDCs (35,460 males and 32,616 females) across six Local Government Areas

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(LGAs) in Benue State, based on data from the Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) Round 11 (March 2023) and the Biometric Registration Progress Report (July 2024). A sample of 384 school-age IDCs was selected using a multistage sampling technique. First, proportional stratified sampling determined the sample from each camp: Makurdi (124), Guma (146), and Logo (113). Within each camp, stratification by gender was applied based on a 52:48 male-to-female ratio. Finally, simple random sampling was employed within each gender stratum to ensure equal selection chances.

A structured questionnaire titled *Impact of Technology in Facilitating Access to Quality Education for Internally Displaced Children Questionnaire (ITFAQEIDCQ)*, adapted from Balogun (2005), was used. The instrument consisted of two sections: Section A (demographics) and Section B (25 items grouped into five thematic clusters). Responses were rated using a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1). Experts in measurement and evaluation validated the instrument for clarity and relevance. Following validation, a pilot test with 20 participants was conducted outside the study area. Cronbach's Alpha yielded reliability coefficients ranging from 0.70 to 0.79 across clusters, with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.89. Data were collected using a direct delivery-and-retrieval method by the researcher and three trained assistants. Clear instructions were provided, and responses were retrieved immediately to minimize non-response and ensure data integrity. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to analyze the research questions, with a mean score of 2.50 or higher indicating a high extent of agreement.

Presentation of Results

This provides concise summary of the data analysis conducted following the administration of the research instrument. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were employed to analyze respondents' responses. These measures facilitated informed decision-making regarding the outcomes of the study.

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: The demographic description of respondents:

Age	Frequency	Percent
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11-13	54	14.1
14-16	186	48.4
17-19	144	37.5
Total	384	100.0
Gender		
Male	196	51.0
Female	188	49.0
Total	384	100.0
Class Level		
JSS1-3	250	65.1
SS1-3	134	34.9
Total	384	100.0
Duration in the IDP camp		
Less than one year	27	7.0
1-2 years	330	85.9
More than 2 years	27	7.0
Total	384	100.0

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Table 1 provides a demographic overview of a sample population (N = 384) with variables categorized by age, gender, class level, and duration of stay in an IDP camp in Benue State.

Age Distribution

The age range of 14-16 years comprises the majority (48.4%) of the population, followed by 17-19 years (37.5%), while 11-13 years accounts for the smallest proportion (14.1%). This suggests that the population is predominantly adolescents in middle-to-late teenage years, likely indicative of the targeted group for the study.

Gender Distribution

The gender ratio is nearly balanced, with males constituting 51.0% and females 49.0%. The near parity ensures gender representation in the study, allowing for potentially unbiased gender-specific analysis.

Class Level Distribution

A significant portion of the participants (65.1%) are in Junior Secondary School (JSS 1-3), while 34.9% are in Senior Secondary School (SS 1-3). This distribution highlights

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the dominance of younger secondary school students, which might influence the type of interventions or programs implemented.

Years spent in the IDP Camp

Most participants (85.9%) have stayed in the camp for 1-2 years, with only 7.0% each having stayed less than a year or more than two years. This indicates a relatively recent displacement, as the majority have spent a moderate duration in the camp. It reflects the likely ongoing impact of displacement on education and other life domains.

Research Question 1: What are the specific technological tools and platforms that have most effectively facilitated access to and enhanced the quality of education for IDPs in Benue State?

To answer this research question, the responses of the students were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results were presented in table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Specific Technological Tools and Platforms that have most Effectively Facilitated Access to and Enhanced the Quality of Education for IDPs

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=383	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Mobile learning apps (e.g., Google Classroom, Edmodo) have been effective in improving my access to education.		2.83	0.61	Agreed
2.	Online video platforms (e.g., YouTube, Zoom) have significantly enhanced my understanding of the subjects taught.		2.96	0.86	Agreed
3.	The use of e-books and digital libraries has improved the quality of my learning experience compared to printed books.		2.53	0.69	Agreed
4.	Educational websites (e.g., Khan Academy) have provided me with quality resources for learning.		2.62	0.89	Agreed
5.	Using computers or tablets has been effective in improving my learning outcomes compared to traditional tools.		2.65	0.89	Agreed
	Grand Mean		2.72	0.78	Below Average

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 2 displays the specific technological tools and platforms that have most effectively facilitated access to and enhanced the quality of education for IDPs in Benue State. All

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item statements recorded mean scores above the established cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating agreement across all categories. With a grand mean of 2.72 and a standard deviation of 0.78, the findings suggest that technological tools and platforms, such as mobile learning apps, online video platforms, e-books, digital libraries, and educational websites, have positively contributed to improving access to and the quality of education for IDPs.

Research Question 2: What are the main challenges and barriers hindering the effective use of technology to facilitate access to quality education for IDPs in Benue State?

To answer this research question, the responses of the students were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results were presented in table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Main Challenges and Barriers Hindering the Effective Use of Technology to Facilitate Access to Quality Education for IDPs

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=383	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Lack of reliable internet access is a major challenge to using technology for my education.		2.95	0.72	Agreed
2.	The high cost of technological devices (e.g., tablets, laptops) hinders my access to education.		3.28	0.59	Agreed
3.	Limited availability of electricity affects my ability to effectively use technology for learning.		3.33	0.60	Agreed
4.	Poor digital literacy among teachers has negatively impacted the quality of education I receive.		2.88	1.06	Agreed
5.	The learning environment in the IDP camp makes it challenging to focus on technology-based education.		2.89	1.01	Agreed
	Grand Mean		3.07	0.80	Below Average

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 5 reveals the main challenges and barriers hindering the effective use of technology to facilitate access to quality education for IDPs in Benue State. All item statements recorded mean scores above the established cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating agreement across all categories. With a grand mean of 3.07 and a standard deviation of 0.80, the findings suggest that challenges such as lack of reliable internet access, the high cost of technological devices, limited availability of electricity, poor

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digital literacy among teachers, and the learning environment in IDP camps have negatively impacted the effective use of technology for educational purposes.

Discussion of Findings

The result of research question one showed that technological tools and platforms, such as mobile learning apps, online video platforms, e-books, digital libraries, and educational websites, have positively contributed to improving access to and the quality of education for IDPs. The positive impact of technological tools and platforms on education for IDPs could be attributed to their accessibility, cost-effectiveness, and ability to deliver diverse, multimedia-rich resources that address varied learning needs. The findings of this align with Munoto, Meini and Satriana (2021), who demonstrated that mobile learning applications improve student responses and motivation, making them a feasible tool for enhancing learning outcomes. Furthermore, the finding agreed with Oyelere and Suhonen (2016), which demonstrated how mobile learning applications like MobileEdu effectively provide access to quality education in Nigeria. Lastly, the study resonates with Dahlstrom, Walker and Dziuban (2013), who found that mobile devices allow students to access educational materials anytime and anywhere, bridging gaps in access to learning resources. This finding implies that the adoption of digital tools and online learning systems can improve access to education for IDP children, offering them equitable and inclusive opportunities for quality learning.

The outcome of research question two revealed that challenges such as lack of reliable internet access, the high cost of technological devices, limited availability of electricity, poor digital literacy among teachers, and the learning environment in IDP camps have negatively impacted the effective use of technology for educational purposes. This result may be attributed to systemic infrastructural deficiencies, socio-economic barriers, and inadequate teacher training in digital literacy within IDP camps. The findings correspond with Adeoye, Adanikin, and Adanikin, (2020), who identified unstable power supply and the high cost of data as barriers to e-learning in Nigeria. Furthermore, the results are consistent with Ubi and Ofre (2021) who opined that poor internet connectivity and the lack of digital tools prevented rural students from participating in government-provided e-learning initiatives. Similarly, Akinrinola, Adebayo, Onakpoya and Nwaozuru, (2020), reported that teachers' limited technical expertise poses a challenge to effective e-learning facilitation. The implication of this finding is that addressing infrastructural deficits, reducing technology costs, and

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improving teacher digital literacy are critical for enhancing the effective use of technology in education within IDP camps.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the positive contributions of technological tools and platforms—such as mobile learning apps, online video platforms, e-books, digital libraries, and educational websites—in enhancing access to and improving the quality of education for internally displaced persons (IDP) children in Benue State. These technologies have provided flexible learning opportunities and enriched educational content, making learning more engaging and accessible. However, significant challenges persist, including unreliable internet access, high costs of technological devices, limited electricity supply, low digital literacy among teachers, and unfavorable learning environments within IDP camps. Addressing these barriers is essential to fully harness the potential of technology in creating equitable and effective educational opportunities for displaced children.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that:

1. Stakeholders should evaluate and scale up the use of platforms such as e-learning modules, interactive educational software, and localized digital libraries that have demonstrated success in improving access and quality.
2. School administrators, in collaboration with government and NGOs, should address infrastructural challenges such as internet connectivity, reliable electricity supply, and the affordability of devices by establishing solar-powered computer labs, providing offline digital tools, and seeking partnerships to secure necessary resources for IDP schools.

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References

- Adewale, S., (2016). Internally displaced persons and the challenges of survival in Abuja. *African Security Review*, 25(2), pp. 176 – 192.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10246029.2016.1154475>
- Akume, A. T. (2015). The question of internally displaced persons (IDPs) in Nigeria: A reflection on present realities. *Journal of Third World Studies*, 32(1), 221-244.
- Alimi, A. E., Babalola, E. O., Aladesusi, G. A., Issa, A. I., & Omolafe, E. V. (2022). Availability and Utilization of Assistive Technology for Learning among Students with Special Needs in Ilorin, Kwara State. *Indonesian Journal of Community and Special Needs Education*, 2(1), 17-28.
- Ambe-Uva, T.N. (2012). The right to education for internally displaced persons in Nigeria through open and distance learning. *Huria: Journal of the Open University of Tanzania / Vol. 13 No. 2 (2012) / Articles*
- Baytak, A., Tarman, B., & Ayas, C. (2011). Experiencing technology integration in education: children's perceptions. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 3(2), 139-151.
- Bekalo, S.A., Brophy, M. & Welford, A.G. (2003). The Development of Education in Post-Conflict 'Somaliland'. *International Journal on Educational Development*, (23), pp. 459-475.
- Bertoni, E., Maio, M. D., Molini, V. & Nistico, R. (2019). Education is forbidden: The effect of the Boko Haram conflict on education in North-East Nigeria. *Journal of Development Economics*, 141(102249).
- Bothe, D. A., Olness, K. N., & Reyes, C. (2018). Overview of Children and Disaster. *Journal of Developmental and Behavioural Pediatrics*, (39), pp. 653-662
- Bothe, D. A., Olness, K. N., & Reyes, C. (2018). Overview of children and disaster. *Journal of Developmental and Behavioural Pediatrics*, (39), pp. 653-662.
- Bulut, O., & Delen, E. (2011). The relationship between students' exposure to technology and their achievement in science and math. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 10(3).
- Courduff, J. (2011). One size never fits all: Tech integration for special needs. *Learning & Leading with Technology*, 38(8), 16-19.

(Assessing the integration of Digital tools and Barriers on ... Ahmed, T. A. & Sunday, O. 2025)

- Dryden-Peterson, S., Dahya, N., & Adelman, E. (2017). Pathways to Educational Success Among Refugees: Connecting Locally and Globally Situated Resources. *American Educational Research Journal*, 54(6), pp. 1011-1047
- Edmonds, R. R. (1979). Effective Schools for Urban Poor. *Educational Leadership*, 37, (1), pp. 15-27.
- Ferris, E. & Winthrop, R. (2010). Education and displacement: assessing conditions for refugees and internally displaced persons affected by conflict. UNESCO. *Education for All Global Monitoring Report*.
- Gibbs, G., Edited by, Flick, U. (2007). *Analysing Qualitative Data*. The SAGE Qualitative Research Kit. SAGE Publications Limited London.
- Hansen, K., (2016). The Relationship between Teacher Perceptions of Pupils Attractiveness and Academic Ability. *British Educational Research Journal*, 42(3).
- Herron, J. (2010). Implementation of technology in an elementary mathematics lesson: The experiences of pre-service teachers at one university. *SRATE Journal*, 19(1), International Society for Technology in Education. (2011). Top ten in '10: ISTE's education technology priorities for 2010. Retrieved from <http://www.iste.org/about-iste/advocacy/top-ten-in-10.aspx>.
- Hogwood, B. W. & Gunn, L. A. (1984). *Policy analysis for the real world*. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Howlett, M. & Ramesh, M. (2003). *Studying Public Policy: Policy Cycles and Policy Subsystems. Second Edition*. Oxford University Press Canada.
- IDMC (2020). *Nigeria: Global report on internal displacement*. Norwegian Refugee Commission: Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre.
- IDMC. (2017). Global report on internal displacement Norwegian Refugee Council. Retrieved from <http://www.internal-displacement.org/global-report/grid2017/>
- Ingutia, R. (2020). Does marginalization in education stall the progress of the sustainable development goals? *International Journal of Primary, Elementary and Early Years Education*, 48(5), pp. 495-511

(Assessing the integration of Digital tools and Enablers on ... Ahmed, T. A. & Sunday, O. 2025)

INSEC [Informal Sector Service Centre] (2007). *Human Rights Yearbook*. Kathmandu: INSEC

Jones, N., Abebe, W., Emire, G., Gebeyehu, Y., Gezahegne, K., Tilahun, K., Workneh, F. & Vintges, J. (2022). Disrupted Educational Pathways: The effects of conflicts on adolescent educational access and learning in war-torn Ethiopia. *Frontiers in Education*. Available at: (DOI: 10.3389/educ.2022.963415).

Kelly, A. (2001). *Benchmarking for Improvement: A practical guide for comparing and improving effectiveness*. Routledge Falmer, New York.

Kim, C., & Rouse, M. (2011). Reviewing the role of teachers in achieving Education for All in Cambodia. UNESCO IBE. Prospects, at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-011-9201-y> (41), pp. 415-428. Available.

Kirk, J. & Winthrop R. (2007). Promoting Quality Education in Refugee Contexts: Supporting teacher development in Northern Ethiopia. *International Review of Education*, (53), pp. 715-723.

Levine, D. U. & Lezotte, L. W. (1990). *Unusually Effective Schools: a Review and Analysis of Research and Practice*. Madison, WI: National Centre for Effective Schools Research and Development.

Ling, M. (2017). Returning to No Home: Educational Remigration and Displacement in Rural China. George Washington University Institute for Ethnographic Research. *Anthropological Quarterly*, 90(3), pp. 715 – 742

Macbeath, J. & Mortimore, P. (2001). *Improving school effectiveness*. St Edmundsbury Press Ltd.

Mattina, G. L. (2018). How persistent is the effect of conflict on primary education? Long-run evidence from the Rwandan genocide. *Economics Letter*, (163), pp. 32 – 35.

Messiou, K. (2012). *Confronting marginalisation in education: A Framework for promoting inclusion*. Routledge Taylor & Francis Group London and New York.

Mowat, J. G. (2015). Towards a new conceptualization of marginalization. *European Educational Research Journal*, 14(5), pp. 454 – 476.

(Assessing the integration of Digital tools and Enablers on ... Ahmed, T. A. & Sunday, O. 2025)

Murphy, J. (2011). Homeless children and youth at risk: the educational impact of displacement. *Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk*, 16(1), pp. 38 – 55

National Emergency Management Agency (2015). Annual report. Abuja: Yaliman press Ltd

National Policy on Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria. Federal Republic of Nigeria, (2014). Available at: <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/5a7ae2324.pdf>.

Nigeria Displacement Tracking Matrix (2024). Round 25 November. Retrieved from <https://displacement.iom.int/Nigeria>.

Obashoro-John, O. A., & Oni, G. J., (2017). Refugee Education: The State of Nigeria's Preparedness. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 5(6), pp. 989-994.

Olakulehin, F.K. (2007). Information and communication technologies in teacher training and professional development in Nigeria. Retrieved from http://gojde.anadolu.edu.tr/tojide25/pdf/article_11.pdf. *Turkish online Journal of Distance education*, 8(1), 133-142.

Olanrewaju, F. O., Olanrewaju, F. O., Alabi, J. O., Amoo, E., Loromeke, E. & Ajayi, L. A. (2019). Insurgency and the invisible displaced population in Nigeria: A Situational Analysis. *Original Research*, pp. 1 -12. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2158244019846207>

Omale, A.A., & S, D. (2022). Education in emergencies and national development: bridging the gap in educating internally displaced children. *Zamfara Journal of Politics and Development*. Vol. 3 No. 3.

Onapajo, H. (2020). Children in Boko Haram Conflict: The Neglected Facet of a Decade of Terror in Nigeria. *African Security*, 13(2), pp. 195 – 211.

Oyelere, S.S., Suhonen, J., & Sutinen, E. (2016). "M-learning: a new paradigm of learning ICT in Nigeria", *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies (iJIM)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 35-44.

Ripat, J. D., & Woodgate, R. L. (2017). The importance of assistive technology in the productivity pursuits of young adults with disabilities. *Work*, 57(4), 455-468.

Stoll, L. & Fink, D. (1996). *Changing our schools*. Open University Press, Buckingham.

(Assessing the integration of Digital tools and Barriers on ... Ahmed, T. A. & Sunday, O. 2025)

Tajudeen, O. A. & Fadeyi, A. O. (2013). Issues of refugees and displaced persons in Nigeria. *Journal of Sociological Research*, 4(1).

Thisday, (2023). *Experts seek increased access to education for disadvantaged children via technology*. Editorial. Thisday Newspaper. Monday, September 31.

Tinio, L.V. (2003). *ICT in education*. Retrieved on August 31st, 2011 from <http://www.en.wikibooks.org/wiki/ICT-in-Education>.

UNESCO (2007). *Manual for pilot testing the use of indicators to assess impact of ICT use in education*. Retrieved on October 1st, 2011 from <http://www.unescobkk.org/education/ICT/resources>.

UNESCO, (2019), Global education monitoring report, Summary, p.26. Retrieved 24th June 2021 From http://www.internaldisplacement.org/sites/default/files/publications/documents/Education%20for%20Internally%20Displaced%20Children_web.pdf.

UNESCO. (2023). *Out-of-school numbers are growing in sub-Saharan Africa | Global Education Monitoring Report*. <https://www.unesco.org/gem-report/en/2022-out-school>

UNHCR – United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (2016) *Connecting refugees: how internet and mobile connectivity can improve refugee well-being and transform humanitarian action* (www.unhcr.org/media/connecting-refugees).

UNICEF (1997b). Population Estimates for Somaliland. UNICEF Zonal Office, Hargeisa.

Uzodinma, U.E., Njoku, O.C., & Ejiofor, J.N., (2024). Assessing the impact of technology integration in enhancing learning outcomes on childhood and primary education in Nigeria: a case study of hill crest preparatory and primary school, Nsukka. *International Journal of Studies in Education* – Vol. 20, Issue 2, 31-41.

Wilson, J.D. (1988). *Appraising teaching quality*. British Library Cataloguing Publication Data

World Bank (2002). *Information and communication technologies: a World Bank group strategy*. Washington, D.C: The World Bank Group.

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